

Linking to the ERGA Pilot BioProject in European Nucleotide Archive

ERGA Pilot Project Guidelines

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Version 1

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Congratulations, you are ready to upload your raw data and/or genome assembly and/or annotation to the European Nucleotide Archive. Here we provide you with guidelines as to how to associate your data with the European Reference Genome Atlas Pilot Project.

Document Overview

In this document we provide instructions on how to register separate projects (studies) for the data types produced by your genome team:

1. Data project with all the genomic and transcriptomic data produced.
2. Analysis project with the genome assembly.
3. Analysis project with the alternate genome assembly (optional).
4. Species overview umbrella project with the data and analysis projects as children.
5. Register and upload sequencing experiments/runs.
6. Register and upload assembly/assemblies.
7. Contact COPO (copo@earlham.ac.uk) and provide them with the BioProject accession of the species umbrella project to have it linked underneath the ERGA Pilot umbrella project.

The first step to submit the data is to access the Webin interface with your ENA/EGA user credentials (<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/submit/webin/login>). Please, register if you do not have an account, yet. Once you are logged in into the system you can register the data and analysis projects by clicking “**Register Study (project)**” on the Dashboard. Go to <https://ena-docs.readthedocs.io/en/latest/submit/study.html> for general details on how to register a project.

Component 1: Data project

Release date: The release date indicates when the study and all its data will be made public. When first registering a project, it can be as much as two years beyond the present date but you can change it at any time to make it sooner or later. Once the data becomes public you may not make it private again. For the pilot project, since sample data is connected to a project only via the sequencing data, we urge pilot participants to make their sequencing read data public as soon as possible, i.e. immediate release.

Short descriptive study title: “<species_name> (<Indigenous_name*>) (<common_name*>), genomic and transcriptomic data”

For example: “Helleia helle (violet copper), genomic and transcriptomic data”

Study Name: <tolid_prefix>

For example: “ilHelHell”

Detailed study abstract: This project collects the genomic and transcriptomic data generated for <linnaean_name>, <indigenous_name*>, <common_name**>, to facilitate genome assembly and annotation. The data was produced in collaboration with the ERGA sample ambassador, <name> (<country>), <Indigenous Peoples or Local Community name***> partner, and the ERGA Pilot Project team. The European Reference Genome Atlas (<https://www.erga-biodiversity.eu/>) is an affiliated project under the umbrella of the Earth BioGenome Project. (<https://www.earthbiogenome.org/>). Please see the ERGA Pilot Project Data Sharing and Management Policy (<https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.8091290>) prior to publication using this data.

For example: “This project collects the genomic and transcriptomic data generated for Helleia helle, the violet copper butterfly, to facilitate genome assembly and annotation. The data was produced in collaboration with the ERGA sample ambassador, Vanesa Arroyo (Andorra), and the ERGA Pilot Project team. The European Reference Genome Atlas (<https://www.erga-biodiversity.eu/>) is an affiliated project under the umbrella of the Earth BioGenome Project (<https://www.earthbiogenome.org/>). Please see the ERGA Pilot Project Data Sharing and Management Policy (<https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.8091290>) prior to publication using this data.”

*Indigenous_name is a non-mandatory field that is to be used only when partnering with and Indigenous Peoples or Local Communities. The name inserted here is the species name that the partnering community traditionally uses to refer to the species using their own Indigenous nomenclature system.

** Optional inclusion

***This is a non-mandatory field used to ensure fair attribution is given to any partnering Indigenous Peoples or a Local Community. However prior to its inclusion, this should be discussed and consent should be obtained from each partner as this information will be publicly displayed on the internet into perpetuity .

The project submission page should look like this:

The screenshot shows the 'Register study (project)' form in the ENA Webin Submissions Portal. The form is divided into several sections:

- Submission Details:**
 - Release date [This is when your study will be made public.] * : 29-06-2023
 - Study Name : ilHelHell
 - Short descriptive study title * : Helleia helle (violet copper), genomic and transcriptomic data
 - Detailed study abstract * : This project collects the genomic and transcriptomic data generated for Helleia helle, the violet copper butterfly, to facilitate genome assembly and annotation. The data was produced in collaboration with the ERGA sample ambassador, Vanesa Arroyo (Andorra), and the ERGA Pilot Project team. The European Reference Genome Atlas (<https://www.erga-biodiversity.eu/>) is an affiliated project under the umbrella of the Earth BioGenome Project (<https://www.earthbiogenome.org/>).
 - Will you provide functional genome annotation ? :
- PubMed Citations Registration:**
 - Add PubMed Citations +
- Study Attributes:**
 - Add Study Attributes +

At the bottom of the form, there are three buttons: 'CNAG' (with a red square icon), 'Submit' (in a green box), and 'Cancel'.

Now you can submit the project. A new window will show up with the assigned project ID, that you can also check in the “Studies Report” tab of the Dashboard. Save this study accession; you will need it below to upload the sequencing data to the ENA.

Component 2: Genome assembly project

Release date: For the pilot project, assembly release date can be set to be released immediately or to be held until time of genome note publication.

Short descriptive study title: <species_name> (<Indigenous_name>, <common_name*>), genome assembly, <tolid>.

For example: “Helleia helle (violet copper), genome assembly, ilHelHell1”.

Study name: <tolid>

For example: “ilHelHell1”

Detailed study abstract: This project provides the genome assembly of <linnaean_name>, <indigenous_name*>, <common_name*>. The data was produced in collaboration with the ERGA sample ambassador, <name> (<country>), <Indigenous Peoples or Local Community name***> partner, and the ERGA Pilot Project team. The European Reference Genome Atlas (<https://www.erga-biodiversity.eu/>) is an affiliated project under the umbrella of the Earth BioGenome Project. Please see the ERGA Pilot Project Data Sharing and Management Policy (<https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.8091290>) prior to publication using this data.

* optional inclusion.

OPTIONAL. If the assembly to be submitted is annotated already and you plan to upload EMBL format files (see section below on Assembly Submission):

1. Tick the box on “will you provide functional genome annotation”
2. Add Locus tag prefix. Click “+” and add the desired locus tag. Then click Add. A locus tag prefix can contain only alpha-numeric characters, must be 3-12 characters long, upper case, start with a letter, and should not contain symbols, such as -_*. We recommend using the specimen TOLID (eg. ILHELHELL1). You can find your sample ToLID on the internal ERGA Pilot_Progress_Tracker document, or through the ERGA Data Portal (https://portal.erga-biodiversity.eu/data_portal). This prefix will need to be added to the ID of each annotated feature (LOCUS).

The project submission page should look like this:

ENA Webin Submissions Portal

[Support](#) |
 [Manage Account](#) |
 [Logout \(Webin-1543\)](#)

Register study (project)

Submission Details

Release date [This is when your study will be made public.] *

Study Name

Will you provide functional genome annotation ?

Short descriptive study title *

Detailed study abstract *

PubMed Citations Registration

[Add PubMed Citations](#) +

Study Attributes

[Add Study Attributes](#) +

Tag	Value	Add
		Add

Locus Tag Prefix Registration

[Add Locus Tag Prefixes](#) +

Locus Tag	Remove
ILHELHELL1	🗑️

CNAG
Submit
Cancel

Now you can submit the project. A new window will show up with the assigned project ID, that you can also check in the “Studies Report” tab of the Dashboard.

Component 3 (optional): Alternate genome assembly project

Release date: For the pilot project, assembly release date can be set to be released immediately or to be held until time of genome note publication.

Short descriptive study title: <species_name> (<Indigenous_name*>, <common_name*>), genome assembly, <tolid>, alternate haplotype.

For example: “Helleia helle (violet copper), genome assembly, ilHelHell1, alternate haplotype”.

Study name: <tolid>, alternate haplotype

For example: “ilHelHell1, alternate haplotype”

Detailed study abstract: This project provides the alternate haplotype genome assembly of <linnaean_name>, <Indigenous_name*>, <common_name*>. The data was produced in collaboration with the ERGA sample ambassador, <name> (<country>), <Indigenous Peoples or Local Community name***> partner, and the ERGA Pilot Project team. The European Reference Genome Atlas (<https://www.erga-biodiversity.eu/>) is an affiliated project under the umbrella of the Earth BioGenome Project. Please see the ERGA Pilot Project Data Sharing and Management Policy (<https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.8091290>) prior to publication using this data.

OPTIONAL. If the assembly to be submitted is annotated already and you plan to upload EMBL format files (see section below on Assembly Submission):

1. Tick the box on “will you provide functional genome annotation”
2. Add Locus tag prefix. Click “+” and add the desired locus tag. Then click Add. A locus tag prefix can contain only alpha-numeric characters, must be 3-12 characters long, upper case, start with a letter, and should not contain symbols, such as -_*. We recommend using the specimen TOLID + H2 (eg. ILHELHELL1H2). This prefix will need to be added to the ID of each annotated feature (LOCUS).

Now you can submit the project. A new window will show up with the assigned project ID, that you can also check in the “Studies Report” tab of the Dashboard.

Component 4 (optional): Co-/Symbiont assembly project

Release date: For the pilot project, assembly release date can be set to be released immediately or to be held until time of genome note publication.

Short descriptive study title: <symbiont_scientific_name> genome assembly, <host_tolid.symbiont_name.version>

For example: “Wolbachia endosymbiont (group B) of Lycaena phlaeas genome assembly, ilLycPhla1.Wolbachia_sp_1.1”

Study name: <host_tolid.symbiont_name.version>

For example: “ilLycPhla1.Wolbachia_sp_1.1”

Detailed study abstract: This project provides the genome assembly of <symbiont_scientific_name>. The data was produced in collaboration with the ERGA sample ambassador, <name> (<country>), <Indigenous Peoples or Local Community name***> partner, and the ERGA Pilot Project team. The European Reference Genome Atlas (<https://www.erga-biodiversity.eu/>) is an affiliated project under the umbrella of the Earth BioGenome Project. Please see the ERGA Pilot Project Data Sharing and Management Policy (<https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.8091290>) prior to publication using this data.

OPTIONAL. If the assembly to be submitted is annotated already and you plan to upload EMBL format files (see section below on Assembly Submission):

3. Tick the box on “will you provide functional genome annotation”
4. Add Locus tag prefix. Click “+” and add the desired locus tag. Then click Add. A locus tag prefix can contain only alpha-numeric characters, must be 3-12 characters long, upper case, start with a letter, and should not contain symbols, such as -_*. We recommend using the specimen TOLID + SY (eg. ILHELHELL1SY). This prefix will need to be added to the ID of each annotated feature (LOCUS). Depending on the co-/symbiont, an appropriate letter could be used, for example “W” for Wolbachia, instead of “SY”.

Now you can submit the project. A new window will show up with the assigned project ID, that you can also check in the “Studies Report” tab of the Dashboard.

Species Umbrella Project Registration

To link the independent projects that will contain the data of one species, we need to register an umbrella project that will become a child of the ERGA Pilot Project and will have as children the data and assembly projects of that species. Instructions on how to register umbrella projects can be found at <https://ena-docs.readthedocs.io/en/latest/faq/umbrella.html>. As stated there, umbrella studies can only be created and updated from the command line, by using curl to submit XML files you have created. Following the ENA documentation, we will show here an example of how the xml files should look and which is the command to submit them.

First, you need to create a **submission.xml** file with the following information:

```
<SUBMISSION>
  <ACTIONS>
    <ACTION>
      <ADD/>
    </ACTION>
    <ACTION>
      <HOLD HoldUntilDate="TODO: release date"/>
    </ACTION>
  </ACTIONS>
</SUBMISSION>
```

It is good practice to provide a specific release date for an umbrella project using the HOLD action in the submission XML. When this date arrives, the umbrella project will become public automatically. However, this is optional and if not provided, the release date defaults to two years after registration. Instead of hold, you can also specify </RELEASE> to have it released immediately. Each child project is released independently and they each have their own hold date which is determined on registration, the umbrella project release does not determine the child project(s) release. For example, if we want the project to be private until March 31st 2022, our submission.xml file would say:

```
<Hold HoldUntilDate= "2022-03-31"/>
```

To release immediately (recommended), don't "hold" it, "release" it:

```
<Release/>
```


Second, create an **umbrella.xml** file with the following info:

Alias: erga-pilot-<tolid_prefix>-study-umbrella-<yyyy-mm-dd>

Name: <tolid_prefix>

For example: “ilHelHell”

Title: <scientific name>

For example: “Helleia helle”

Description: This project collects the sequencing data, genome assemblies, and genome annotation generated for <linnaean_name>, <Indigenous_name>, <common_name>. The data was produced in collaboration with the ERGA sample ambassador, <name> (<country>), <Indigenous Peoples or Local Community name***> partner, and the ERGA Pilot Project team. The European Reference Genome Atlas (<https://www.erga-biodiversity.eu/>) is an affiliated project under the umbrella of the Earth BioGenome Project. Please see the ERGA Pilot Project Data Sharing and Management Policy (<https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.8091290>) prior to publication using this data.

Child project accessions: Data project, Genome assembly project, Alternate genome assembly project

You can add more child projects by inserting more <RELATED_PROJECT> blocks, or you can remove a block from this example if you only wish to add one project at this time.

If we continue with our *H. helle* example, this file would look like:

```
<PROJECT_SET xmlns:xsi="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema-instance">
  <PROJECT center_name="Andorra Recerca i Innovacio" alias="ilHelHell1">
    <TITLE>Helleia helle</TITLE>
    <DESCRIPTION>This project collects the sequencing data, genome assemblies, and genome annotation generated for Helleia helle, the violet copper. The data was produced in collaboration with the ERGA sample ambassador, Vanesa Arroyo (Andorra), and the ERGA Pilot Project team. The European Reference Genome Atlas (https://www.erga-biodiversity.eu/) is an affiliated project under the umbrella of the Earth BioGenome Project. Please see the ERGA Pilot Project Data Sharing and Management Policy prior to publication using this data.
    </DESCRIPTION>
  </PROJECT/>
  <RELATED_PROJECTS>
```



```
<RELATED_PROJECT>
  <CHILD_PROJECT accession="PRJEB_-----" />
</RELATED_PROJECT>
<RELATED_PROJECT>
  <CHILD_PROJECT accession="PRJEB_-----" />
</RELATED_PROJECT>
</RELATED_PROJECTS>
<PROJECT_ATTRIBUTES>
  <PROJECT_ATTRIBUTE>
    <TAG>Keyword</TAG>
    <VALUE>ERGA</VALUE>
  </PROJECT_ATTRIBUTE>
</PROJECT_ATTRIBUTES>
</PROJECT>
</PROJECT_SET>
```

When you are satisfied with the changes you have made to umbrella.xml you should run the following command from the directory in which both XML files are located:

```
curl -u Webin-acctnum:yourWebinPssWd -F "SUBMISSION=@update.xml" -F \
"PROJECT=@umbrella.xml" "https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/submit/drop-box/submit/"
```

You must edit the command to include your Webin account ID and password. You will receive a receipt in XML form. You should note the 'success' attribute which will be true or false to indicate success or failure of your submission. If the submission was successful, the receipt will also contain the accessions of your project. These begin 'ERP' and 'PRJEB'. The receipt for a failed submission will contain error messages which will advise you on how to fix your submission. Send this PRJEB accession number to COPO (see end of this document).

Read Submission

After registering the study and samples, you can submit the reads referring to them. Note that samples and studies will only be associated after experiments have been submitted. Raw read submissions can be performed either interactively, programmatically or via webin-cli. Details on how to carry out read submission in any of these 3 ways can be found at: <https://ena-docs.readthedocs.io/en/latest/submit/reads.html>.

All genomic and transcriptomic data, ideally in “fastq.gz” format, used in the project needs to be submitted under the data project named “<species name>, (<indigenous_name>) (<common name>), genomic and transcriptomic data” created previously, above.

Assembly Submission

After registering the projects, samples and runs, a genome assembly can be submitted. This submission will refer to a project (the project for the assembly that we registered before), a sample, and one or more runs. The genome assembly can be submitted to the ENA annotated or unannotated. Detailed instructions on how to perform this step can be found at: <https://ena-docs.readthedocs.io/en/latest/submit/assembly.html>. To simplify the submission process, we have included here some recommendations.

Before submitting your assembly, consider the highest level of assembly which has been obtained. ENA recognizes three assembly levels. An assembly may contain a mixture of the three sequence types:

- Contig: the highest level of assembly is contigs.
- Scaffold: the highest level of assembly consists of gapped contigs (scaffolds).
- Chromosome: the highest level of assembly includes assembled chromosomes.

The aim of the ERGA is to obtain chromosome level assemblies, but in some cases this may not be possible. Also note that lower-level assemblies (eg. contigs or scaffolds) can be updated to chromosome-level after submission. The term “chromosome” in this context will include both the nuclear and organellar chromosomes as part of the same submission.

The following instructions show how to submit a genome assembly in chromosome-level, but with the ENA guide and this example, you should be able to submit other level assemblies as well. Before assembly submission some files need to be prepared. First of all, a manifest file that will define the essential metadata shall be submitted with the following structure:

- Field name (first column): case insensitive field name
- Field value (second column): field value

The following metadata fields are supported in the manifest file for genome context:

- STUDY: Study accession - mandatory
- SAMPLE: Sample accession - mandatory
- ASSEMBLYNAME: Unique assembly name, user-provided - mandatory
- ASSEMBLY_TYPE: 'clone or isolate' - mandatory
- COVERAGE: The estimated depth of sequencing coverage - mandatory
- PROGRAM: The assembly program - mandatory
- PLATFORM: The sequencing platform, or comma-separated list of platforms - mandatory
- MINGAPLENGTH: Minimum length of consecutive Ns to be considered a gap - optional
- MOLECULETYPE: 'genomic DNA', 'genomic RNA' or 'viral cRNA' - optional
- DESCRIPTION: Free text description of the genome assembly - optional
- RUN_REF: Comma separated list of run accession(s) – optional

Various file name fields are supported in the manifest file. Note that all of these are optional, though of course at least one must be provided, and some may only be relevant in the presence of other file types. The available fields are as follows:

- FASTA: sequences in fasta format
- FLATFILE: sequences in [EMBL-Bank flat file format](#)
- AGP: sequences in [AGP format](#)
- CHROMOSOME_LIST: list of chromosomes
- UNLOCALISED_LIST: list of unlocalised sequences

In the following page (<https://ena-docs.readthedocs.io/en/latest/submit/assembly/genome.html>) you will find instructions on how to prepare each of the files. As a general idea, keep in mind that you need to provide the assembly either as a FASTA or a FLATFILE. In case you do not want to submit the annotation, you should just give a FASTA file with all the sequences in your assembly. However, if you want to provide the annotation, an EMBL file should be produced and submitted with the FLATFILE option. This EMBL file needs to follow the [ENA format recommendations](#).

- The CHROMOSOME_LIST file must be provided when the submission contains assembled chromosomes. The file is a tab separated text file (USASCII7) up to four columns.
- OBJECT_NAME (first column): The unique sequence name, matching with the sequence name in your FASTA file (> line) or EMBL flat file (AC * line). This corresponds to field 1 of the *.chromosomes.csv file returned by the rapid curation scripts from GRIT.
- CHROMOSOME_NAME (second column): The chromosome name. The value will appear as the /chromosome, /plasmid or /segment qualifier in the EMBL-Bank flat files. There are some restrictions on the values that this field should contain, check the ENA link pasted before for details. We recommend this to be a number, if the chromosome number is known. In case the mitochondrial genome is submitted, its value can be “MT”. This corresponds to field 2 of the *.chromosomes.csv file returned by the rapid curation scripts from GRIT. Primary assemblies should contain the mitogenome, while alternate assemblies should not. The same goes for chloroplast genomes: use “Pltd” as the chromosome name.
- CHROMOSOME_TYPE (third column): Allowed values:
 - chromosome
 - plasmid
 - linkage_group
 - monopartite
 - segmented
 - multipartite
- CHROMOSOME_LOCATION (optional fourth column): By default, eukaryotic chromosomes will be assumed to reside in the nucleus and prokaryotic chromosomes and plasmids in the cytoplasm. Check the possible values in the ENA page.
- The UNLOCALISED LIST file should be provided when the submission contains chromosomes with unlocalised sequences. Unlocalised sequences are contigs or scaffolds that are associated with a specific chromosome but for which order and orientation is unknown. These can also be found in the *.chromosomes.csv file, and are designated as *_unloc*. The unlocalised list file is a tab separated text file (USASCII7) containing the following columns:
 - OBJECT_NAME (first column): the unique sequence name matching a FASTA header or flatfile AC * line
 - CHROMOSOME_NAME (second column): the unique chromosome name associated with this sequence. This must match with a CHROMOSOME_NAME in the chromosome list file.

- The AGP file might be used to describe the assembly of scaffolds from contigs or of chromosomes from scaffolds.

Once all the files needed for assembly submission are ready, they need to be validated, uploaded and submitted using the Webin command line submission interface (Webin-CLI). Please refer to the Webin command line submission interface documentation for full information about the submission process.

IMPORTANT: Link the species umbrella project to the ERGA Pilot

Similar to how you created/updated your species umbrella project, COPO must update the ERGA Pilot umbrella project with your “child” project, itself a species-level umbrella project. Write to COPO (copo@earlham.ac.uk) and provide them with the BioProject accession of the species umbrella project to have it linked underneath the ERGA Pilot umbrella project.